

Methodological Guidelines on Sectoral Value Chain Analysis

Improving existing value chain by implementing
nature-based-solutions

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the task

The fundamental goal of this task is to examine how the Nature-based Solutions (NbS) can be mainstreamed within value chains in different sectors of the MERLIN project. Our key research question is: **How are NbS linked to sectoral value chains via Case Studies (CS), and in what ways do they help to solve value chain problems?**

Attaining this objective necessitates an extensive overview of sectoral value chains, an understanding of a variety of Case Studies (CS), whether associated with the MERLIN project or not, the capability for comparative analysis, and insights into labelling and certification. This methodological guideline is designed to itemise the requisite skills and knowledge, thereby assisting sectoral partners in Task 4.4 to collaborate and achieve their goals. As practitioners will be the essential actor in reality to implement, promote and ultimately mainstream NbS in different sector, the mission of this task will be essentially to identify potentials in the general or specialised value chain to connect business sectors to the NbS, to make practitioners realise that implementing NbS is not only an extended responsibility related to the social responsibility or a type of “green marketing” for existing businesses, but also a method which can bring true commercial benefits to their business.

1.2 Activities of this task

Given the diverse skills and knowledge this task demands, we have developed a sequential guideline to streamline the process. This document offers methodological advice rather than a mandatory protocol, providing general directions for undertaking the task. The implementation of these steps will vary based on each sectoral team's level of expertise and their knowledge in areas relevant to the task. However, we strongly advise adherence to the expected output elements to facilitate seamless writing and cross-sectoral integration. Task 4.4 is broken down into four key exercises:

- Exercise 1: Value Chain Mapping
- Exercise 2: Use CS of NbS to Address Value Chain Problems
- Exercise 3: Review of Standards
- Exercise 4: Sectoral Value Chain Discussion

1.3 An adaptive methodological framework

Building on the previous sub-section's insights, an adaptive methodological framework has been chosen for this task, acknowledging the specific needs of diverse sectoral partners. This framework will evolve through the creation of different versions as the work progresses, while maintaining stable core steps and elements. It will also be fine-tuned to better suit each sector by adjusting minor, sector-specific aspects.

This approach is conceptualised based on two key considerations. First, the complexity of sectoral Value Chain Analysis (VCA) arises from the varied nature of the sectors involved, the extensive range of stakeholders, and the numerous internal and external CS. Creating a one-size-fits-all methodological framework that is universally applicable across all sectors is a significant challenge. Second, an adaptive framework aligns better with pragmatic requirements, as it allows for customisation according to the distinct VCA knowledge levels of sectoral partners, thereby facilitating more effective task completion.

In the **current version (v2.0)**, with sectoral partners completing the first two exercises and gained necessary knowledges and insights on their sector, our focus extended from the first two exercises to the third and fourth exercises, which imply a more profound knowledge on the sectoral specificities and search for more specialised information, rather than staying on the general understanding of the working sector required in the first two exercises.

1.4 Involved MERLIN sectors

Currently, the sectors involved in Task 4.4 remain among [Agriculture](#), [Insurance](#), [Peat Extraction](#), and [Water Supply](#). These sectors have been identified due to their relevance and potential impact in the context of VCA:

Agriculture

Insurance

Peat Extraction

Water Supply

1.5 Roles and responsibilities

- General task mentoring: [Gerardo Anzaldua](#) (Ecologic)
- Task content lead: [Jianyu Chen](#) (JHI)
- Methodological framework: Levin Scholl (Ecologic) & [Jianyu Chen](#) (JHI)
- Data gathering and analysis: Sectoral partners
- Deliverable writing: Sectoral partners & JHI
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 - Agriculture: [Géza Gelencsér](#) (WWF-Hungary)
 - Insurance: [Audrey Vion Loisel](#) (iCatalist)
 - Peat Extraction: [Alhassan Ibrahim](#) (JHI)
 - Water Supply: [Marine Boulard](#) (Aqua Publica Europea)

1.6 Workplan

KEY DATE	MILESTONE
20 December 2023	First release of T4.4 methodological guideline document
29 January 2024	Submission of draft report for outputs from Exercise 1 and 2
19 February 2024	Report ready for Exercise 1 and 2
18 March 2024	Release of updated methodological guideline document
29 April 2024	Submission of draft report for outputs from Exercise 3 and 4
13 May 2024	Report ready for Exercise 3 and 4
27 May 2024	First draft of D4.4: Integration of all draft reports for all Exercises
24 June 2024	Second draft of D4.4
19 August 2024	Final draft of D4.4

For any questions related to this document or related to the general VCA task, please contact the content lead [Jianyu Chen](#)

2. Conceptual framework for working with value chains

This section explores the essential concepts central to Task T4.4, complemented by guiding questions. The initial focus is on the concept of "value" from an inter-subjective perspective, contrasting with the traditional econometric approach. Following this, the structure of the value chain within this inter-subjective value context is examined. The section also analyses various alternative chain conceptions, an important step in clearly defining a value chain as distinct from other components of comprehensive chain analysis. The selected definition of VCA is intended to assist sectoral partners in identifying the analytical elements necessary for the successful implementation of the VCA task.

2.1. What are value chains?

What is value?

To research value chains, it is essential but also helpful to understand what 'value' is. In the context of a market economy, the value of goods and services is often indicated by their price. As we are so used to the price as an indicator for value, we often think of 'price being equivalent to 'value' as an inherent attribute of goods and services. However, the price is just an indication of economic value and not the foundation of value in and of itself. So, what constitutes 'value'? Value is the perceived worth of something. Value can be based on tangible aspects of a thing, such as its scarcity and material utility. Value can also be based on the intangible aspects of a thing, such as its cultural, psychological, or emotional significance. The subjective nature of value means that different individuals and cultures value different things to different degrees and depending on the specific context. Very often prices are inadequate to capture the actual value of something (e.g., fresh air, friendships, sentimental objects, etc.). However, the price generally indicates the collectively assigned value of goods and services within a market-economy, informed by the supply and demand of multiple market actors.

What is the value chain concept?

A value chain is a sequence of economic activities that add value to a product. A value chain typically starts with research and development or the cultivation or mining of raw materials, continues with various processing activities, and ends with the distribution to the final consumer along with any customer services. Along this sequence of activities, the product is transferred from one economic actor to another, typically by selling and buying the product. Each actor transforms

the product to enhance its value. Accordingly, each activity adds value in one way or the other. Each value-adding actor along the value chain tries to capture some of the generated value, by reselling the transformed product at higher price. As discussed above, value can be very subjective and can be based on intangible aspects such as personal taste or the prestige associated with a brand name.

EXAMPLE 1: THE COFFEE VALUE CHAIN

In the coffee production value chain, various actors play key roles:

1. **Farmers (Primary Producers):** The process starts with coffee farmers who cultivate and harvest the coffee beans. They are the primary producers in the value chain.
2. **Processing:** After harvesting, the coffee cherries need to be processed to extract the beans. This may involve methods such as drying, pulping, and fermentation.
3. **Exporters:** Once the coffee beans are processed, they are sold to exporters who aggregate beans from various farmers. Exporters ensure quality control and prepare the beans for international shipment.
4. **Roasters:** Coffee beans are then sold to roasters who roast the beans to develop flavours. Roasters may also blend different types of beans to create unique coffee blends.
5. **Retailers:** Roasted coffee beans are supplied to retailers, which can include coffee shops, supermarkets, and online platforms. Retailers may package the coffee for sale to end consumers.
6. **Coffee shops:** In the case of coffee shops, baristas play a role in brewing and serving coffee to customers, adding a service component to the value chain.
7. **Consumers:** The end consumers purchase and enjoy the final coffee product. The value chain is complete when the consumers perceive value in the coffee's quality, taste, and overall experience.
8. **Each actor in the value chain contributes to the overall value of the coffee product.** Farmers add value through cultivation and harvesting, processors through the preparation of the raw beans, exporters by ensuring quality and facilitating international trade, roasters by developing distinct flavours, and retailers by making the product accessible to consumers. The end goal is to provide a high-quality coffee experience to the end consumer while optimizing the efficiency of each stage in the chain.

EXAMPLE 2: THE SMARTPHONE VALUE CHAIN

In the smartphone value chain, the process begins with Research and Development, progresses through manufacturing, marketing, and distribution, and concludes with customer support—a comprehensive cycle from innovation to consumer assistance:

1. **Research and Development (R&D):** The process begins with R&D, where engineers and designers work to create innovative features and technologies for the new smartphone.
2. **Raw Material Acquisition:** Once the design is finalized, the company needs raw materials such as metals, plastics, and electronic components. This involves relationships with various suppliers worldwide.
3. **Manufacturing:** The raw materials are then transformed into the actual smartphone through manufacturing processes, which may occur in multiple locations globally.
4. **Marketing and Branding:** The finished smartphones are marketed to create awareness and desire among consumers. This includes advertising, creating promotional materials, and building the brand image.
5. **Distribution:** The smartphones are then distributed through various channels, including wholesalers, retailers, and possibly directly to consumers through online sales.
6. **Retail:** The smartphones reach retail stores or online platforms, making them accessible to consumers. This step involves the physical or digital presentation of the product to potential buyers.
7. **Sales:** Consumers purchase the smartphones, either in physical stores or online, completing the transaction.
8. **Customer Support:** After the sale, customer support comes into play, addressing any issues, providing assistance, and enhancing customer satisfaction.
9. Each of these stages contributes to the overall value of the smartphone in the eyes of the consumer. The value chain perspective allows businesses to analyse and optimize each step to enhance the overall value delivered to the customer while managing costs effectively.

Other 'chain' concepts

The supply chain concept is very similar to the value chain concept. Like the value chain concept, the supply chain concept describes a sequence of processes involved in producing and delivering a product to the end consumer. However, the supply chain concept is less oriented towards value generation and focuses more narrowly on the logistics and operational processes involved in getting a product from A to B. While the value chain concept accommodates a wide range of research topics, the supply chain concept is used by central companies within a given chain to ensure the procurement of their inputs and the distribution of their outputs.

Other chain concepts offer yet distinct perspectives on economic processes. Global commodity chains centre on the international trade of major commodities (e.g., metals, minerals, grains, etc.), to study globalization and economic development, emphasizing the interconnectedness of various actors and economies in the global market. On the other hand, Michael Porter's value chain concept delves into the internal operations of a firm, dissecting its activities across departments to analyse value generation within the firm. Focused on improving a firm's competitiveness, it scrutinizes how each firm function contributes to the overall value of the firm's output.

Although all these chain concepts share certain aspects in common, it is important to be aware of their conceptual differences to avoid confusion and remain conceptually sharp. Despite this, value chain researchers may adopt any of these other chain concepts to employ their perspectives, theories, and methods, depending on the specific research question.

2.2. What is value chain analysis?

Value Chain Analysis (VCA) is a comprehensive examination of various analytical elements to understand the complex dynamics within a value chain. Different stakeholders engage in VCA for reasons aligned with their distinct goals. For instance, businesses conduct VCA to enhance competitiveness, improve product value, or strategize for new market entries. Governments and policymakers use it to formulate policies and address industry-wide issues, while researchers focus on how value, power, risks, and costs are distributed among chain actors, and how value chains evolve over time. The focus of a VCA can vary depending on the specific objectives, emphasizing certain elements while de-emphasizing others.

Key analytical elements for a VCA typically include:

- **Actors:** A diverse array of actors may shape the value chains, including producers, traders, processors, service providers, wholesalers, retailers, consumers, cooperatives, associations, and other stakeholders such as local communities, NGOs, activists, or the media.
- **Activities:** The value chain encompasses a sequence of activities, such as production, primary and secondary processing, logistics and transportation, storage, packaging, marketing and distribution, regulatory oversight, and additional services like auditing, certification, insurance, financing, or consultancy services. Each activity contributes to the overall value of the final product or service.
- **Value chain governance:** A value chain involves repeated interaction of various actors. This interaction can be organized by different forms of governance, which differ in their degree of explicit coordination by a leading actor. The most explicitly coordinated form of governance is a vertically integrated firm, owning and controlling the entire chain. The least explicitly coordinated form of governance is a market-structure, in which multiple actors trade with one another without exercising control over the respective others. In between are governance forms dominated by a central lead firm, which exercises control over the other value chain actors.
- **Natural Environment:** The natural environment comprises the natural resource base or raw materials but also other ecosystem services along the chain (including provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services). Moreover, the natural environment is the basis of environmental risks to the chain, such as those posed by climate change. Sustainability concerns like biodiversity loss and pollution further underscore the importance of environmental considerations along the chain.
- **Institutional Framework:** The institutional framework, shaped by policies, laws, regulations, taxes and subsidies plays a pivotal role in guiding the activities within the value chain. Understanding the regulatory landscape is crucial for a comprehensive analysis.

- **Other External Factors:** External factors exert considerable influence, encompassing market forces, technological innovation, consumer demands, public pressure, and other dynamics.

Considering these analytical elements, the following bullet points suggest six general steps to conduct a value chain analysis (VCA):

1. **Define your objective:** Clearly state what you aim to achieve with your sectoral VCA. This goal should align with the general purpose of T4.4. For reference, see the [Purpose of the task](#).
2. **Selecting Entry Points:** Identify an entry point for analysis that aligns with your specific goals, considering the diverse actors and activities involved. This could include specific key actors, a particular activity, the governance structure of the chain, or a certain regulation. While starting with Exercise 1 is recommended, other methodological options are also available (for more information, see [Related to the exercise 1 and 2](#)).
3. **Prioritizing Value Chain Components:** Recognize the varying significance of different actors, activities, and other elements within the value chain, and prioritize them based on their impact.
4. **Collecting Relevant Data:** Ensure that data collection covers all key actors, activities, and the governance structure of the chain. Also, focus on the natural environment, the institutional framework, and other external factors to meet the objectives of your analysis. Data can be gathered from academic literature, grey literature, project reports, interviews, databases, workshops, among other methods.
5. **Analysing Data:** This phase involves mapping the selected value chain, assessing how value is added along its various activities, and analysing how the chain is influenced by the natural environment, the institutional framework, and other external factors.
6. **Identifying Constraints and Development Opportunities:** Thoroughly scrutinize the entire value chain for bottlenecks, constraints, and potential development opportunities that align with your objectives and motivations, while also considering the broader institutional, environmental, and external factors.

3. Four exercises for completing sectoral value chain analysis

This section outlines common methodological guidelines and provides practical examples to assist sectoral partners in executing Task T4.4, focusing on sectoral VCA. The analysis process is segmented into four distinct exercises, each offering an opportunity for sectoral partners to engage in in-depth analysis and reflection on the VCA. These exercises are designed to encourage partners to adopt both top-down and bottom-up approaches by addressing the following research questions:

1. **Identifying the Generic Value Chain:** What constitutes the generic value chain in the given sector, adequately representing most actors, activities, the natural environment, and the institutional framework of that sector?
2. **Defining and Addressing Value Chain Problems:** Can any issues be categorized as ‘value chain problems? How do NbS contribute to addressing these problems? Which actors and activities are most closely linked to NbS?
3. **Impact of NbS Implementation:** How can the implementation of NbS in certain elements of the value chain potentially enhance or resolve existing value chain problems?
4. **High-Level Reflections:** After completing the prior exercises, what lessons can be derived about the drivers and barriers to implementing NbS within the value chain under current circumstances?

Through these exercises, sectoral partners can gain a comprehensive understanding of their respective sector's value chain, identify and address specific problems, and reflect on the broader implications of implementing NbS.

Related to the exercise 1 and 2

We advise sectoral partners to initiate Task T4.4 by engaging in the first two exercises. This recommendation is practical, as the outcomes of Exercises 1 and 2 will be presented at the MERLIN all-partner meeting (26–29th February 2024 in Vienna, detailed in the [Workplan](#)). Moreover, completing these initial exercises is expected to enhance understanding of the VC concept and provide a broader knowledge base VCA. However, as highlighted in the section on [An adaptive methodological framework](#), the sequence of undertaking Exercises 1 and 2 is not rigid. Sectoral partners have the discretion to start with either, depending on their expertise and specific understanding of the VCA and sectoral realities:

- **Commencing by the Exercise 1:** This is a common approach for beginning T4.4. Mapping out the generic sectoral value chain can offer a foundational understanding of the stakeholders,

their institutional framework, and production activities in the sector. We advocate for a rapid iterative method, focusing initially on a rough sketch of the value chain that is broadly applicable across the sector, rather than striving for perfection. This approach allows partners to refine their understanding and adjust the value chain after completing Exercise 2, which involves identifying specific Case Studies (CS) and reflecting back on the first exercise.

- **Commencing by the Exercise 2:** This involves identifying relevant CS at the outset, usually focusing on more niche sub-sectors. Beginning with Exercise 2 leads to an immediate engagement with a specific sub-sectoral value chain related to the products and services being analysed. In this case, there's no need to develop a generic sectoral value chain initially; the focus is directly on a more detailed sub-sectoral analysis.

Both approaches offer unique insights and are designed to be adaptable to the varying expertise and sectoral contexts of the partners.

3.1. Exercise 1: Value Chain Mapping

Exercise 1, centred on Value Chain Mapping, is a pivotal step in comprehending and analysing the dynamics of sectoral VC within the MERLIN project. This exercise is designed to create a detailed graphical depiction of the value chain, encompassing a range of analytical elements crucial for understanding the structure and operations of each sector. This section begins with a general introduction to the exercise, elucidating its objectives. It then proceeds to introduce a variety of graphical tools and reflective methods aimed at facilitating the effective completion of this task. Examples of value chain map are also provided to help sectoral partners to intuitively grasp the form of the expected output from the Exercise.

3.1.1. Introduction

What is the expected output of this exercise?

The primary output of this exercise is a graphical flowchart that visually represents the value chain, accompanied by a briefing that connects various analytical elements. For a refresher on these elements, refer to the subsection [What is value chain analysis?](#). It is important to note that the value chain mapping is not only a numeration of implicated actors and activities, relationships between actors and activities needs also to be presented to understand the flow of the values and value added process through each step of the value chain.

What is the purpose of this task?

Value chain mapping is instrumental in developing a generic structure of a value chain within your sector. It helps in identifying the roles of ecosystems and ecosystem services within the chain. This exercise will enhance your familiarity with the value chain approach and provide a foundational structure for more detailed value chain maps in subsequent exercises, such as Exercise 2.

What is value chain mapping?

Value chain mapping is part of the VCA that aims to identify main and supportive business activities and all related components and the relationships between them in the corporate value chain (Umberger, 2014). It enables analysts to gain an overview of the value chain, visualize networks and relationships, understand the chain's structure, and become aware of all actors, markets, and factors (e.g., infrastructure, policies, processes) that affect the chain's performance.

3.1.2. Mapping of your value chain

The main task in this exercise is to delineate your value chain using relevant analytical elements. Tools like [Miro](#), [ProcessOn](#), [XMind](#), or even PowerPoint can facilitate this mapping and reflection process. Emphasize the role of the natural environment as it is pertinent to MERLIN. Begin your value chain mapping by considering questions adapted from a World Bank report on value chains (Webber & Labaste, 2007):

- **Actors:** Identify actors in your sector's VC at each stage of production/service-providing activities. Who are the supportive actors? How are they organized to deliver products/services to end customers? Which actors are more significant?
- **Activities:** What are the activities each actor performs in the VC? Describe the value-adding activities in production/service provision and sales.
- **Value-adding stages:** At what points in the VC is value added to the final product/service?
- **Key actors:** Who are **the most important** actors within the value chain?
- **Value chain governance:** Is the value chain controlled by a principal actor or multiple actors? How is power distributed among them, e.g., collaborative or dominated by a principal actor?
- **Natural environment:** What natural resources are involved in this value chain? What risks might actors face when exploiting these resources?
- **Institutional framework:** Describe the institutional framework, including relevant policies, laws, regulations, taxes, and subsidies affecting the actors' activities.
- **Your own role:** What is your role within this value chain? What potential impact could you have in the future?

3.1.3. Examples of Value Chain Mapping

Figure 1. General Value Chain Mapping of Global Textile production (flow chart)

Figure 2. General Value Chain Mapping of Steel production (Sankey chart)

Figure 3. General Value Chain Mapping of Forestry and Wooden Furniture (UML chart)

3.2. Exercise 2: Use Case Studies of NbS to Address on Value Chain Problems

Exercise 2, advancing from the groundwork laid in Exercise 1, engages sectoral partners in a practical application of their initial value chain mapping. The primary objective in this phase is to investigate specific instances where NbS have been successfully implemented to address value chain challenges. This task entails an in-depth review of various CS, sourced both internally within the MERLIN project and externally, to illustrate the effectiveness of NbS in resolving sectoral value chain issues.

In addition to providing a basic introduction to essential concepts useful for undertaking this exercise, a structured two-step methodology is proposed to guide the participants through the process. This methodical approach is designed to facilitate a thorough and systematic exploration of NbS applications, thereby enhancing the sectoral partners' understanding of integrating NbS into their respective value chains.

3.2.1. Introduction

What is the expected output of this exercise?

Upon completion of this exercise, you are expected to provide a [detailed Value Chain Map and a briefing of sectoral VCA](#) from the perspective of chosen CS, either internal or external to the MERLIN project. The primary criterion for selecting CS should be their relevance in addressing or solving value chain problems. These problems' definition will be elaborated later. Chosen CS may relate to one or several actors or activities in the value chain. The next reflection on the selected CS will be based on if there is, or there is technically potential, to implicate NbS to solve the value chain problem.

What is the purpose of this task?

This exercise aims to achieve two objectives. Firstly, to deepen understanding of the sectoral VC through CS where NbS have been implemented, refining the VC map created in Exercise 1. Secondly, to comprehend the role of NbS in the sectoral VC and how they can address value chain problems.

What defines a problem as a value chain problem?

A **value chain problem** refers to issues or challenges that occur within the sequence of activities involved in creating a product or service, from its conception to its delivery to the end-user. In general, we can ask the question as ‘*What and where are the bottlenecks in the value chain?*’ (Webber & Labaste, 2007). These problems can significantly impact the efficiency and effectiveness of the value chain. Key aspects include:

- **Supply chain disruptions:** These are issues associated with obtaining essential raw materials, parts, or components for production. For example, in the metallurgical industries, a significant problem could be the depletion of ore mines, leading to supply shortages.
- **Production inefficiencies:** These involve difficulties in manufacturing processes that result in waste, quality issues, or delays. Such inefficiencies may hinder the value addition to products/services, impacting end-user satisfaction. An historical instance is the use of aluminium ornament on Napoleon’s military uniforms, while others use gold or silver ornaments, for once it was challenging to extract and refine aluminium, unlike precious metals, making it more valuable.
- **Distribution challenges:** In the context of goods, these are difficulties in transportation leading to delays or increased costs. For services, the challenge might be in persuading end-users to access them, which can also incur additional costs.
- **Marketing and sales issues:** These are problems encountered in effectively promoting or selling products to the target market. In the context of the MERLIN project, a challenge might be expanding the reach of products and services related to Nature-based Solutions (NbS). This is why reviewing existing standards in each implicated sector and exploring the potential of certification is crucial.

To better address the value chain problems, an overview of the level of value chain problem is useful:

1. **Single-step VC problems:** problems which impact on only one step on the value chain, as a direct application of value chain examples listed above. However, as a value chain step can imply one or several activities, a single-step VC problem can also impact on several activities or actors, depending on the specificity of the value chain step.
2. **Multi-step VC problems:** problems which impact on at least two steps on the value chain. These impacted steps can be conducted by one or more than one actor, and more than two activities.
3. **Whole-level VC problems:** usually comes from external environments such as market impact, market evolution, change of regulation or legislation, which will impact on the

continuity of the sector and the existence of the industry. Either change of the business model or the whole VC need to be changed to cope with those problems.

Addressing value chain problems is vital for optimizing the value chain, enhancing efficiency, reducing costs, and improving the overall quality of products or services. In an era where enterprises and organisations are increasingly cognizant of their environmental impact and are assuming more environmental responsibility, resolving value chain problems through the implementation of NbS offers strategic benefits.

What are NbS?

The 5th United National Environmental Assembly (UNEA) in 2022 agreed on the definition of nature-based solutions as “*actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services, resilience and biodiversity benefits*” (UNEA, 2023). This definition of NbS can be applied into a large range of areas for socio-economic activities, not only covering all involved sectors, but also being consistent with the general MERLIN project objectives.

3.2.2. Step 1: Data collection

If Exercise 1 has been completed, the initial step in Exercise 2 focuses on gathering data on Case Studies (CS) and integrating them into the value chain mapping framework developed previously. It's important to note that a well-documented process at this stage is essential for effectively completing the briefing writing step.

- **Identify NbS Applications:** Your task is to identify instances where Nature-based Solutions (NbS) have been used to address specific value chain problems. This can be achieved through desk research or conducting interviews. In situations where linking NbS to the sectoral Value Chain (VC) is challenging, both internal and external CS from the MERLIN project can be utilised.
- **Conduct VCA Based on CS:** Perform a VCA on these specific sectoral value chains as per the identified CS (for reminding what to do in a VCA, see the sub-section [What is value chain analysis?](#)). The aim is to understand how NbS contribute to solving value chain problems in your sector. This should involve a careful examination of actors, activities, VC governance, the institutional framework, the natural environment, and other external factors. The analysis could start from a specific value chain problem, asking, ‘*We have a problem here,*

but can we use NbS to solve it?, or from an NbS perspective, exploring where and how it fits into the value chain and its relation to actors and activities, by asking: *'In this CS, we have solved a problem by NbS, where we can locate it on our value chain map? To which actor and activities it is related?'*

- **NbS Focus on Specific Aspects:** NbS in CS typically do not address the entire value chain problem but rather focus on specific actors or activities. Use the insights from these CS to make your generic value chain map (from [Exercise 1: Value Chain Mapping](#)) more detailed and specific.
- Find out how the NbS was implemented, see questions asked in the 3rd bullet point of (question a to e).
- **Investigate NbS Implementation:** Delve into the details of how NbS was implemented in each case. Refer to the questions outlined in the third bullet point of [Step 2: Write the CS](#), which includes questions from (a) to (e).

3.2.3. Step 2: Write the CS briefing

In the second step of Exercise 2, the briefing should encompass the following key points:

1. **Refinement of Value Chain Map:** Utilize the VC map from Exercise 1 as a foundation to create a more specific sectoral VC map. Focus on areas where NbS were employed, detailing the VC map to reflect these specificities.
2. **Description of VC Problem:** Clearly describe the identified value chain problem. Explain how this problem has impacted the sectoral value chain, particularly focusing on its negative effects on actors and activities.
3. Detailed Explanation of NbS Implementation:
 - a. Implementing and Funding Actors: Who was the implementing actor? Who was the funding actor?
 - b. NbS Initiative: What was the initiative of the NbS?
 - c. Governance of NbS: How was the NbS implementation governed? It is governed by who?
 - d. Implementation Challenges: What were obstacles to implement the NbS? How were they overcome?
 - e. Enabling External Factors: What external factors have enabled the implementation, e.g., policies, service providers, etc.?

4. Impact of NbS on Resolving VC Problem:

- a. Beneficiaries of NbS Implementation: Who benefited from the implementation of the NbS? In a long-term or short-term.
- b. Benefits to Actors: What benefits did the NbS bring to the actor?
- c. Extent of Problem Resolution: To what extent the NbS helped to resolve the value chain problem, partially or entirely?

3.3. Exercise 3: Review of Standards

3.3.1. Introduction

What is the purpose of this task?

This task aims to provide a thorough understanding of how current industry standards within your sector might [support freshwater ecosystem restoration and the implementation of NbS](#). Industry standards play a crucial role in facilitating coordination along value chains and cooperation between different value chain steps. This exercise seeks to ascertain how these standards can direct practices towards the adoption of NbS and freshwater ecosystem restoration (especially river restoration in our cases). Consequently, we aim to identify potential improvements to these standards, enhancing their effectiveness in promoting the uptake of NbS within sectoral value chains. For this exercise, we will utilise the [International Trade Centre's Standard Map](#), as to our knowledge, it is the most extensive database on sustainability standards across various sectors and industries that we can find. This resource allows for a specific comparison and evaluation of numerous standards, leading to a comprehensive analysis.

What is the expected outcome of this Exercise?

The objective of this exercise is to deliver a structured set of recommendations in three distinct parts, informed by the insights gained in Exercise 2, where we pinpointed specific challenges within the value chain and assessed the potential for implementing NbS.

Given potential time constraints, it is NOT necessary to exhaustively examine all existing sectoral standards. Focus should instead be placed on areas previously identified in Exercise 2 where we see opportunities to implement NbS. This approach is intended to alleviate the extensive research burden on sectoral partners concerning the multitude of existing standards within the sector. The three key components of this task are outlined as follows:

1. **Briefing Review of Existing Standards:** Begin by gathering existing standards relevant to the identified value chain problems and organise them into a coherent list. This list should be categorised according to the typologies which will be discussed in the subsection of [What are the different types of standards? \(page 27\)](#). Each standard should be succinctly described, noting the specific stage in the value chain it addresses, the activities and actors involved, and any existing labelling or certifications that advise the consumer that these standards are being met.
2. **Analysis of Standards:** Evaluate the current standards to determine their alignment—or lack thereof—with the integration of freshwater NbS within the sector. This analysis should scrutinise the solutions proposed by existing standards, certifications, or labelling, identifying who is responsible for their implementation. [If there is no standards requiring](#)

freshwater restoration or NbS approaches, please note this observation. In the case of absence of standards on freshwater NbS, attention can be paid to other freshwater-related standards. For instance, there may exist standards focusing on water efficiency but none promoting the restoration of freshwater habitats. It would be useful to discuss the potential ramifications of standards that do not draw attention to ecological water use or other missing aspects of NbS standards in the value chain.

3. **Recommendations for Standard Improvements:** Propose enhancements to the existing standards to facilitate a more effective incorporation of NbS. This may involve suggesting modifications or alternatives to the current solutions that better embody NbS principles. Highlight the potential benefits of such changes, including how the integration of NbS into these standards could enhance business performance by increasing financial gains, ensuring alignment with forthcoming regulatory frameworks, and solidifying the industry's long-term legitimacy.

3.2.3. Standards, certification and labels

What are industry standards?

Industry standards refer to the widely recognised norms or criteria specific to certain sectors. These standards aim to guarantee the quality, safety, efficiency, and compatibility of products, services, and systems within those industries. The development of these standards is typically undertaken by leading figures in the industry, specialised expert groups, or established standard-setting bodies, such as the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) or the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

These standards encompass a broad array of areas, including but not limited to product design, manufacturing procedures, environmental considerations, and the well-being of workers. The formulation of a standard is a rigorous process that necessitates thorough research, the input of subject matter experts, and a consensus among all involved stakeholders. Upon its establishment, a standard serves as the definitive gauge for assessing quality and performance within its respective industry.

While companies generally adopt these standards on a voluntary basis, they can occasionally evolve into mandatory regulatory requirements. Compliance with these standards is often essential for gaining and maintaining market access, as failure to adhere can result in loss of market share or damage to reputation.

What is the role of standards?

Standards serve as a fundamental mechanism for coordination and communication within value chains, which are often characterised by their complexity and opacity. Their role in enhancing the efficiency and transparency of value chains includes several key aspects:

- **Common Framework:** Standards provide a universally understood set of criteria or rules that various stakeholders in the value chain—such as suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and consumers—can follow. This common framework ensures consistency and reliability across all stages of the value chain.
- **Quality and Safety Assurance:** By establishing specific levels of quality and safety, standards ensure that each component, process, or service within the value chain meets these predetermined benchmarks. This assurance is crucial for maintaining trust and reliability among value chain participants.
- **Reduction of Transaction Costs:** The clear guidelines provided by standards help reduce uncertainties and misunderstandings among value chain actors, leading to more streamlined operations and lower transaction costs.
- **Environmental Compliance:** Environmental standards enable companies to minimise their ecological impact and adhere to legal and regulatory requirements, contributing to more sustainable value chain practices.
- **Market Differentiation:** Adherence to high standards can set companies apart in competitive markets where quality, reliability, and sustainability are highly valued. This differentiation can lead to premium pricing strategies and enhanced brand reputation.
- **Visibility and Trust:** The value added by adherence to standards often hinges on their visibility and the trust they engender among consumers and other value chain participants. This is where certifications and standard labels come into play, providing tangible proof of compliance, and contributing to the overall trust in the value chain.

In summary, standards facilitate coordination, enhance efficiency, assure quality and safety, support environmental sustainability, enable market differentiation, and underpin trust within value chains, thereby playing a critical role in their overall effectiveness and sustainability.

What are the different types of standards?

The classification of industry standards can be broken down into several key categories, each targeting different aspects of products, services, and business practices. These include:

- **Quality Standards:** These standards are centred around the quality of products or services, aiming to ensure their consistency, safety, and reliability. An example is the ISO 9001 standard, which sets out the criteria for a quality management system and is one of the most widely recognized standards in this category.

- **Environmental Standards:** Focused on minimizing negative impacts on the environment, these standards promote sustainable practices and responsible resource management. The ISO 14001 standard, which specifies requirements for an effective environmental management system, is a prime example.
- **Safety Standards:** These standards are designed to protect the safety of both products and services as well as workplace environments, ensuring that they are free from risks that could cause harm. In the United States, the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) sets out comprehensive standards for workplace safety across various industries.
- **Technical Standards:** Pertaining to the technical specifications and interoperability of products and systems, technical standards ensure that different components can work together seamlessly. The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) is known for developing a wide range of standards in the field of electronics and electrical engineering.
- **Ethical Standards:** Encompassing social responsibility, these standards address issues related to ethical sourcing, labour rights, and other social concerns. The Fair-Trade certification is an example of an ethical standard that ensures fair treatment and proper compensation for producers in developing countries.

Between certification and labels

Certifications and labels, while interconnected, serve distinct purposes in the context of industry standards.

Certifications represent formal acknowledgements granted by impartial third-party entities, affirming that a particular product, service, or organisation has met the stipulated criteria defined by specific standards. These recognitions serve as a seal of approval, evidencing compliance with established benchmarks related to various aspects such as quality, safety, environmental sustainability, or ethical practices.

The process of obtaining certification typically involves a thorough evaluation or audit carried out by the certifying body. This examination ensures that the necessary requirements, as outlined by the relevant standards, are fulfilled. Thus, while standards provide the framework or "rulebook" delineating the essential requirements, certifications act as tangible evidence that these requirements have been adhered to successfully.

Labels, on the other hand, are visual or textual markers used on product packaging to communicate a product's compliance with certain standards to consumers. Typically, labels are manifested as logo on product packaging, indicating that specific certification has been granted. The purpose of label is to distil complex information about compliance of standards into easily recognizable symbols or terms, making it simpler for consumers to understand the product's adherence to specific criteria.

What are labelling?

Labelling is the act that standard label logos are printed on product packaging to communicate the product meets certain standards and the specific certification is granted.

Therefore, from the label logos, consumers could easily tell the differences between products that are compliant or not to specific standards. Therefore, labelling plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between complex industry standards and the final consumer:

- Labelling act as a succinct and effective means to communicate compliance with various standards to final consumers. They distil complex information about production processes, quality controls, and ethical considerations into easily recognizable symbols and terms. For example, an 'Organic' label on food products instantly informs consumers that the product meets established organic farming standards.
- Trust is built when consumers consistently get the quality and standards that these labels promise. Over time, labels from reliable certifying bodies gain credibility or adapt to consumers' preferences, and their presence on products becomes a factor for many consumers. This trust extends beyond individual products and can enhance the reputation of the brands that use these labels.
- Labelling can significantly add value to products. They differentiate products in a crowded market, allowing them to command a premium price. For instance, products with an '*Natureland*' label might be preferred by environmentally conscious consumers willing to pay more for sustainable food.

In summary, certifications are about obtaining formal recognition of compliance through a rigorous verification process, while labelling is about communicating this compliance and other product attributes directly to the consumer in a simplified and accessible manner.

3.3.2. Operational guide: Review of existing standards with Standards Map

To explore how current industry standards might support objectives in ecosystem restoration and the implementation of NbS, please adhere to the following steps:

- 1) **Accessing the Database:** Visit the [Standards Maps database by the International Trade Centre](#) website. This database offers a comprehensive overview of various standards across different industries, facilitating comparison based on specific criteria.
- 2) **Sector Selection:** In the database interface, navigate to the "Sector" section on the [left side menu](#). Choose one or several categories that align with your industry (as you may not find the terms matching exactly your MERLIN sector). If you're uncertain about which to choose, you can explore each to determine which provide the most valuable insights for your purposes.
- 3) **Geographical Focus:** Scroll down to the "Origin" section on the [left side menu](#) and select "Europe" to tailor the standards to a European production context relevant to your sector.
- 4) **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):** Proceed to the "SDGs" section and choose standards themes in which you are interested. Most common aspect in our project will be "Life below water" and "Life on land" which focus on standards pertinent to these

environmental areas. However, if you are interested in other aspects such as “climate action” or “reducing inequality” etc., feel free to explore.

- 5) **Consumer label (or not):** Navigate to the bottom of the webpage and choose “Yes” under the Consumer label option, it will allow you focusing on standards that display labelling to end-users (consumers) of the product. If you identified in Exercise 2 value chain steps that do not including consumer label displaying, you might want to leave this option empty, which allows you to see all standards.
- 6) **Standard Selection for Comparison:** The database will now display standards relevant to your selections. Use the “Compare” feature [on the right side of each displayed standard](#) to select standards for detailed comparison. Exclude any standards you know are not applicable to our research aim. If uncertain about a standard’s relevance, click the “profile” icon for more details.
- 7) **Comparison Table:** After selecting the last standard for comparison, [a pop-up will appear](#) with a “take me there” link, leading you to your comparison table. Change the view to “Table (advanced)” from the “View” drop-down menu.
- 8) **Focus of the standards:** Choose the focus of standards which you are interested in, we recommend any focus related to the “Environment” and subsequently the “water”, “Biodiversity” and “climate” sub-sections by clicking the “+” icon. Review the criteria listed under the chosen focus and note those relevant for NbS and ecosystem restoration.
- 9) **Criteria Comparison:** Start comparing the selected standards based on criteria important for NbS and ecosystem restoration. Click on “More Info +” for detailed criteria analysis. Assess at least the following criteria, and feel free to include others if considered as relevant:
 - a) Criteria on habitat/ecosystem restoration/rehabilitation.
 - b) Criteria for net positive gain in biodiversity.
 - c) Criteria on natural wetlands and/or watercourses affected by production.
- 10) **Go back and adding more standards in the comparison:** if you want to go back and add more standards in the comparison view, you need to open the new browser tab on holding “ctrl” (Windows) or “cmd” (Mac) button and clicking on the “identity” tab on the top of the webpage. The software currently does not support detailed searching in the compare view, you need to note down the name of the standard on the spreadsheet and type in the name of the standards to add it into the compare.

* *N. B.* Unfortunately, since the Standards Map doesn't allow data download, we'd have to manually copy the relevant criteria information for each standard into spreadsheet. Adjust the template as necessary and [note any criteria not addressed by certain standards, as this information is also valuable.](#)

3.3.3. Comparative analysis on standards

Upon completing the table with industry standards and associated criteria relevant to NbS and ecosystem restoration, evaluate the data by addressing these questions:

- How many, if any, standards relate to freshwater restoration or NbS?

- What are the notable similarities and differences among the standards concerning relevant criteria?
- Which standards explicitly require restoration (over mere protection), and under what conditions? Are there specific requirements for freshwater restoration?
- Identify the most ambitious standard in terms of ecosystem improvement, providing justification for your choice.
- Determine who is responsible for implementing the necessary measures.
- Compile a list of all mentioned measures and activities within the criteria that could support restoration and NbS.
- Reflect on the current standards' effectiveness in facilitating value chain coordination to promote or mandate ecosystem restoration or NbS. Discuss the reasons for your conclusions.

3.4. Exercise 4: Sectoral Value Chain Discussion

What is the purpose of this task?

The purpose of this task is to generate a summary of the previous three exercises. However, this “summary” needs to go beyond a simple recapitulative or a synthesis of previous information, by addressing the following questions:

- What are the most important ecosystem services for the main actors/institutions who guide or implement NbS for your value chain? Please explain how these services support the different actors and processes along the value chain.
- What are lessons learned from the CS, regarding improving the value chain with NbS and restoration? Refer to common barriers/challenges and observed approaches to overcome these challenges (e.g., value chain governance and coordination, policies and standards, technology, and innovation, supporting services such as insurance, finance, etc.).
- Apart from recommendations made for existing standards in Exercise 3, can you think of any further (hypothetical) potential to improve your sector’s value chains using NbS beyond what you identified in the CS? Consider other relevant ecosystem services in your sector, and see if these services could be improved through NbS? Also consider pressures such as climate change that will change the context of your sector and how your sector might have to adapt.
- What factors from the institutional framework or other external factors could advance the use of NbS in your value chain if they were changed?
- What other aspect would you like to highlight that help people to understand how to mainstream restoration and NbS in your sector’s value chains?

What is the expected outcome of this Exercise?

The expected outcome of this Exercise is a brief report for summarising the first 3 Exercises by answering the mentioned questions.

4. References

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